

FIXA-T'HI. A digital territory to promote environmental education

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Abstract: FIXA-T'HI is a learning environment conceived to promote environmental education among students in secondary education. It is based on the interaction between two maps: a geographical representation of the territory of Catalonia, and a collaborative constructed map which is the result of the relationships between images, words and places. The web-based collaborative system supports situated learning, encouraging the participation of learners in the construction of knowledge. It has been successfully applied in a pilot pedagogic experience but needs still to be tested in a large scale implementation, with the participation of multiple schools.

Introduction

The application of Internet-based tools in education has contributed to the breaking down of some of the boundaries that had been previously established in a traditional pedagogic model in which learning took place in the classroom, subject matters were well delimited areas of knowledge, and teaching was mostly instructing. In the web-based learning spaces, education is not restricted to the classroom, but it extends onto space of the Web; subject-matters are considered open areas of knowledge that intersect and inter-relate; and students can take more active roles participating in the construction of knowledge in collaborative learning environments.

In recent years, the popularization of the social web has given a new impulse to the use of Internet as educational space. Blogs, wikies, social bookmarking or folksonomies, and photo and video sharing facilitate the exchange of information and the contact between people. Information sharing technology has existed since the beginning of the Web, but the widespread use of these tools over recent years has transformed them into a social phenomenon. Social software has the potential to support informal learning by augmenting group interaction and collaboration and promoting social interaction and information exchange with web-based environments (Barlett-Bragg 2006). Moreover, these tools can be part of a blended learning model integrating them with classroom-based teaching activities. This requires new pedagogic frameworks which integrate learning content, pedagogic methods and technology in a meaningful and innovative manner. As Mejias argued, "It is relatively easy to incorporate new technologies into the learning process if the goal is merely to replicate the traditional ways of doing things without significantly disturbing institutional values. But what is more difficult, and for this very reason perhaps a more worthy exercise, is to introduce new technologies while we step back and question the pedagogic principles that inform our educational models" (Mejias 2005).

Image repositories and web-based learning environments

Since the year 1999, our research group has been developing web-based environments to support collaborative learning in education, particularly in the field of architecture and design (Madrazo 2004, 2005). Some of these environments consist of image repositories that allow students to store, tag, comment on and relate images. Working on the experience we had gained with the creation of these web-based image repositories, we undertook the task of creating a new learning environment to promote environmental education in secondary schools in Catalonia called FIXA-T'HI (<http://www.salle.url.edu/arc/fixathi/web/index.htm>) in the year 2003. The system was completed in 2005 and it was first applied in the academic year 2006/2007.

In FIXA-T’HI students describe their physical and cultural environment with images and associated concepts that are placed on a map of the territory. Based on this information, the system suggests relationships between images and concepts that learners are expected to explain with short texts. The network of relationships created between users and the system gives rise to a digital territory: a map of relations between images and words, between people and places.

When we first began with the project, applications like Google maps were not available. Also, the use of photo sharing tools like Flickr was not as widespread as it is now. Indeed, the growth in the widespread use of these tools coincided with the completion of our system. Therefore, the decision we adopted was to create our environment from scratch; something we would probably need to reconsider if we had to create it today.

Maps as representations and maps as diagrams

A map, according to the English Oxford Dictionary is “a flat diagram of an area of land or sea showing physical features, cities, roads, etc.” and, more generally, “a diagram or collection of data showing the arrangement, distribution, or sequence of something”. According to the first definition, a map is a representation of a territory while, in the second, it is considered a cognitive tool to grasp the inner structure and functioning of a system. A map which represents a territory is meant to be an analogue or a copy of the depicted area. A system of representation imposes its own constraints in order to transform the actual territory into an analogue image (e.g. the spherical globe projected in a rectangular area, reducing its size and its level of detail by a scale factor). In a map which is thought of as cognitive tool, the likeness between a territory and its representation does not come into play. A concept map, for instance, does not have a scale or boundaries.

This distinction between a map as depiction and as a cognitive tool has been stressed by Deleuze and Guattari in their book *Thousand Plateaus*. In this text, they distinguish between tracing and mapping. Tracing means to reproduce something as it is known (e.g. visualized) beforehand. Mapping, on the other hand is not prefigured by any representation, but it is the result of experimenting directly with the real. It can be thought of, therefore, as an abstract mechanism or machine: “The map is open and connectable in all of its dimensions; it is detachable, reversible, susceptible to constant modification. It can be torn, reversed, adapted to any kind of mounting, reworked by an individual, group, or social formation.” (Deleuze & Guattari 1987). A map understood in this way does not represent reality, but it is immanent to it. The visual representation of the map would be the tracing which is performed over it.

This map in a permanent state of change is a plateau located at an intermediate position between the real and the copy. This notion of mapping turns out to be quite appropriate to understand much of what is happening in the Web nowadays. The continuous process of construction of relationships involving information (images, videos, texts), people (as internet addresses as well as individuals), and places (as spots at the earth represented on the screen as well as physical locations), is an example of a mapping activity taking place at an intermediate space in which both the reality and its representation participate. In Internet, maps stand for both a depiction of an outer reality and as autonomous mechanisms that can create their own reality. They are interfaces between our experience and our knowledge of the world, providing an image of it from which new knowledge can be generated (Dopico 2003).

FIXA-T’HI: description of the learning environment

In Catalan, the verb “fixar”, like the verb “to fix” in English, means to set or place definitely and also to pay attention to something. FIXA-T’HI is an environment which encourages students to observe their environment (natural, urban, cultural, and social) and to assign meanings to places constructing collaboratively a map which is both a representation of the territory and a diagram of relationships.

The construction of the map (e.g. the map of relationships built in collaboration) starts as each student places images on to a representation of territory of Catalonia in which the capitals of the regions are depicted as crosses (Fig. 1). The images and their associated concepts are placed on this representation of the territory on the selection of the

corresponding cross. Images can represent an urban space or landscape, an object or building, a local event or celebrity.

Figure 1: Interface to link images and concepts to the representation of the territory.

From the individual perceptions, a collective map of relations -the digital territory generated from the individual perceptions of the environment- can be built in interaction with the system. To do this, a student first searches in the interface for concepts or images which mean something to him or her. This is a discovery process which is performed by clicking on the images and words which have been previously uploaded by different students. The concepts and images distributed on the territory are meant to be a knowledge map which helps a community of learners to derive knowledge from it in collaboration (Lambiotte et al. 1984). To facilitate the reading of the words, a filter can be used to display only those that start with the characters typed at the bottom input line.

An abstract machine to link images and concepts

Once the student has identified a relevant topic –either through images or through words– the selection becomes an input for a new interface (Fig. 2). This interface is an abstract machine that automatically searches for relations between images and words previously inserted by students.

Figure 2: Interface to elicit meanings from images and words.

Each of the three windows is a channel displaying images and associated words in a different region. If a student introduced an image at region A with the concept “tourism” attached to it, and a second student from the same region introduced another image with the same word attached, both images would appear in this channel when the word “tourism” was selected.

In each channel, the continuous rolling of images or words can be stopped at will. When a word is blocked, then the machine searches for all images to which it has been associated. Images appear sequentially with the intention of suggesting multiple associations as if a brainstorming was taking place along with the system. When a meaningful relation between an image and a word is found, the user clicks on the image to stop the rolling. Alternatively, an image can be blocked and associated words displayed sequentially on the screen. In much the same way, the user clicks on the word as he or she identifies a meaningful relation with the selected image. This procedure of alternative selection of images and words can be repeated in each of the three channels.

If the user needs additional words for searching, the complete vocabulary – consisting of the words introduced by all users – is available on the screen, so that a word can be dragged and dropped on a channel.

Understanding the connection between images and words becomes a fundamental pedagogic activity to carry out with the support of the system. With this associative machine the relationships between images and words operate in multiple directions: an image can illustrate the meaning of a concept and, conversely, a word can give meaning to an image.

When the content of the three channels has been fixed, the user is requested to describe in a short text the meaning that the triad of images and words convey. This task entails a higher level of complexity in the understanding of the relationships between images and words. At this point, it is not about the relationship between an image and a word that comes into play, but the overall context –the description or narrative– that makes the compound of three images and three words meaningful. When the narrative is completed, the triad is mapped onto the representation of the

territory, moving back to the first interface. The triad created in this way can in turn be selected by subsequent users, to be used a new input to the associative machine.

Along with these interfaces, there is another environment for teachers to manage the work of the groups (Fig. 3). Here they can register students with their name and email address, and have a quick look at the work they are doing, without having to search for it in the other interfaces. In this way, there is a clear distinction between those interfaces that foster creativity and discovery from those that have a purely administrative purpose.

Figure 3: Interface to manage group work.

Pedagogic implementation

An early prototype of FIXA-T'HI was first introduced during a workshop dedicated to visual art education in 2005 (Madrazo et al. 2005). The complete system could finally be implemented during the academic year 2006-2007 in a course with students of the School of Education Sciences, Blanquerna, at the Universitat Ramon Llull in Barcelona. A summary of the work done can be found at the project website. Also, a blog was created to provide parallel support to the learning activities (<http://fixathi.blogspot.com/>).

As we prepared the pedagogic application, it became clear that the potential of this learning environment lies in its capacity to interweave different subject matters of the curriculum: linguistics (working with vocabularies, writing short narratives), computing (learning web publishing, image editing), graphic representation (photography), geography (knowledge of the territory) and history (local traditions). In order to confirm this hypothesis though it is still necessary to describe in detail the learning outcomes and competences that students would achieve by participating in the learning activities carried out with (and within) FIXA-T'HI.

Around forty students participated in a two-month course working with two teachers, under the supervision and technical assistance of our research group. The task assigned to students was to describe the environment of their

native region with FIXA-T'HI. The collaborative construction of the map promoted a situated learning model where knowledge is co-constructed through the interaction of learners.

According to the questionnaires completed by students after the course, they considered the experience innovative and exciting. Even though the task appeared to be too abstract at the beginning, they quickly grasped the pedagogic goals as they started to interact with the system. There were no technical difficulties reported that hindered the realization of the learning activities. Unfortunately, in this pedagogic implementation we could not count on the participation of different schools. Organizational difficulties (allocating additional time in the curriculum of schools for extra-activities, coordinating the timetables in different schools and different teachers) have hindered the participation of multiple schools in the learning activities. Therefore, the potential of the system to promote the creation of learning communities, cutting across physical, disciplinary and geographic boundaries and involving a large number of participants, still needs to be tested.

Conclusions

Even though some of the functionalities of FIXA-T'HI can now be found in applications like Google maps, Flickr or Panoramio, there is a distinctive feature which sets our environment apart from existing social software: its pedagogic purpose. The social web encompasses a pedagogic potential that still needs to be unfolded. A project like FIXA-T'HI suggests ways in which the intersection of the social web with education can create meaningful learning environments.

References

- Barlett-Bragg, A. (2006). Reflections on pedagogy: Reframing practice to foster informal learning with social software. *Informal Learning and Digital Media*, Odense, Denmark. (<http://www.dream.dk/uploads/files/Anne%20Bartlett-Bragg.pdf>)
- Deleuze, G. & Guattari, F. (1987). *A Thousand Plateaus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
- Dopico, L. (2003). Afanes cartográficos. Para un mapa de síntomas. *A mínima. New Media-Art Now*, 19, 98-103.
- Lambiotte, J. G., Dansereau, D. F., Cross, D. R., & Reynolds, S. B. (1984) Multirelational Semantic Maps. *Educational Psychology Review*, 1 (4), 331-367.
- Madrazo, L., Hernández, M., Agustí, J. (2005). Taller de percepció de l'entorn FIXA-T'HI. *Construcció de territoris digitals. Congrès d'educació de les arts visuals*, Terrassa (Barcelona).
- Madrazo, L. (2005). NET_CITY: A Collaborative Environment to Promote the Understanding of the Contemporary City. *Journal of Urban Technology*, (12), 21-47.
- Madrazo, L. (2004). Understanding the image in the digital culture: the quest for an interdisciplinary and collaborative education. *ED MEDIA*, Lugano, Switzerland,
- Mejias, U. (2005). A Nomad's Guide to Learning and Social Software. *The Knowledge Tree*, (7) (http://knowledgetree.flexiblelearning.net.au/edition07/download/la_mejias.pdf).

Acknowledgements

The project has been developed by a group from ARC Enginyeria i Arquitectura La Salle (<http://www.salle.url.edu/arc>) led by Leandro Madrazo. Mario Hernández was responsible for the graphic design of the maps as well as for the programming of the associative machine. Jordi Agustí programmed the interface of the territory as well as the administration environment. Joan Galván was responsible for the technical implementation in the pilot pedagogic experience. The map interfaces have been programmed with Flash, and the administration environment with DHTML. We would like to thank our colleagues at the Faculty of Education Sciences Blanquerna, Professor Miquel Àngel Prats and Professor Xavier Àvila, who collaborated in the pedagogic application with their students during the course 2006/2007, for their support and insights.